

Crystal Forms and Melting Behavior in cold-crystallized vs. melt-crystallized Syndiotactic Polystyrene

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SUMMARY: Syndiotactic polystyrene has been known to possess polymorphic crystals. Normally, α and β forms are obtained with melt-processed s-PS. Combination of various fractions of α -type (hexagonal) and β -type (orthorhombic) crystals exists in melt-crystallized syndiotactic polystyrene (s-PS) if crystallized at lower temperatures (240°C or lower), or majority of β -type if at temperatures higher than 260 °C. Slow-cooled s-PS samples in simulation of typical processing cycles were investigated in this study. The DSC results revealed that there are three (or fewer depending on the temperature of melt-crystallization) sharp melting peaks (labeled as Peak-1, -2, and -3, respectively) for the s-PS sample melt-crystallized. The first two peaks are relatively minor while the highest peak is prominent. With annealing at higher temperatures for various times, the first peak (Peak-1) was elevated to a higher temperature and increased in intensity rapidly while Peak-2 was also elevated to higher temperatures but its intensity decreased. Peak-3 remained at the same temperature regardless annealing but decreased in intensity rapidly. X-ray result suggested that β -type crystal is largely associated with the melting entity of Peak-1, and α -type is associated with Peak-2 and Peak-3. Crystal forms in cold-crystallized sPS were compared to those in melt-crystallized one. sPS is commonly used in glass-reinforced forms. Investigation on possible effects of glass fiber on morphology, polymorphism, and properties of sPs is in progress and will be reported in the meeting.

KEYWORDS : crystal structure, DSC, crystallization, s-PS, crystal forms

INTRODUCTION

Most semicrystalline polymers possess only one type of unit crystal cell; for others, polymorphisms are known to exist.[1-3] Normally, α and β forms are obtained with melt-processed s-PS. For melt-processed s-PS, combination of both α and β forms is obtained, but

formation of the β form is proposed to be favored over the α -form in s-PS compression-molded under pressure.[4] The β form is also favored if s-PS is prepared by solvent casting at high temperatures,[5] as well as from melt with particular control of temperature and time of crystallization. Guerra et. al.¹ and De Rosa et. al. [2] also found that crystallization of s-PS from melt produces different fractions of α and β forms depending on cooling rate. In addition, recent studies pointed out that melt-crystallization at high temperatures preferentially favors the formation of β -form.[6,7]. In addition, miscibility can also effect a preferential change in polymorphic behavior in sPS [8,9]. Evans, et al.[10] studied on thru-thickness variation of structure and morphology in injection-molded s-PS, and they found that relative fractions of α - and β -type crystals were different between the skin and center regions, indicating that thermal histories led to variation of the relative proportions of these two crystal types. By imposing thermal treatment on s-PS samples in simulation of actual processing cycles, this study intended to investigate effects of thermal history on micro structure of s-PS.

EXPERIMENTAL

Semicrystalline syndiotactic polystyrene (s-PS) was obtained as a courtesy sample material from Idemitsu Petrochemical Co., Ltd. (Japan) with $M_w = 241,000$ g/mol and $PI (M_w/M_n) = 2.31$. A polarized-light microscope (Nikon Optiphot-2, POL) was used for characterizing optical homogeneity of blends. A small quantity of the melt-blend samples was transferred to between micro-glass slides, heated and pressed into thin film on a heating stage, and examined using the optical microscope. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC-7, Perkin-Elmer) equipped with a mechanical intracooler was used for determining the melting transition temperatures and enthalpy of melting peaks. A uniform heating rate of 10 °C/min was used in scanning unless otherwise specified. If different scanning rates (lower or greater than 10 °C/min) were used for special purposes, they were specified in texts or graphs. The X-ray instrument used was Rigaku D/Max II-B with copper K_{α} radiation and a wavelength of $1,542$ Angstroms. For direct comparison, specimens of X-ray characterization were prepared using the similar thermal treatments as described for the thermal analysis samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the X-ray diffractograms for s-PS samples after melting at 300 °C for 5 min: (A) naturally cooled by convection, (B) slow-cooled in hot stage (approximately -5 ~ -10 °C/min), (C) slow-cooled in DSC cell (-10 °C/min exactly). Interestingly, characteristics peaks of the β -crystal form ($2\theta = 6.1$, and 12.3°) are absent from the naturally convection-cooled s-PS (Sample-A). The Sample-B and Sample-C contain approximately same fractions of α and β -type crystals.

Diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 6.7, 11.7, 13.2, 15.6,$ and 17.8° are typical of α' -form according to Guerra. et. al. [11] The three peaks at $2\theta = 6.7, 11.7,$ and 17.8° are β' -crystal according to De Rosa et. al. [2] The peak at 20.2° is characteristic of α and β forms and is present regardless of thermal treatment.

Fig. 1. X-ray diffractograms of sPS samples. (A) Naturally cooled sPS from melt state; (B) Slow-cooled in hot stage after melting; (C) Slow-cooled in DSC cell ($-10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$).

Further X-ray characterization studies performed in this laboratory [7] as well as others [12] on melt-crystallized s-PS have proven that for the s-PS samples subjected to crystallization/annealing at higher temperatures, the relative fraction of β crystal is higher and the fraction of α -form becomes lower. For brevity, X-ray diffractograms are not shown, but the sPS melt-crystallized at 260, 250, 240°C , respectively were characterized. The results showed a clear trend of decreasing α -form with increased crystallization temperatures.

Fig. 2 shows the DSC thermograms (all scanned $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) of the s-PS samples subjected to various thermal histories after melting (for 5 min) at 300°C : (A) naturally cooled in air, (B) cooling $-5\sim-10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, (C) cooling $-10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Apparently, the thermograms exhibited differences in multiple melting. All curves display a prominent Peak-3, but the intensities of Peak-1 and Peak-2 are different. The naturally cooled s-PS exhibited only Peak-2 and Peak-3. The X-ray result (in Fig. 1) indicates that this sample possesses majority of α -type and little fraction of β -type. By comparison, the two samples cooled exactly $-10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ or approximately $-5\sim-10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ exhibited similar melting behavior as well as similar relatively fractions of α - vs. β -type crystals.

Fig. 2. DSC thermograms (10 °C/min) of sPS samples. (A) naturally cooled sPS from melt; (B) slow-cooled in hot stage; (C) slow-cooled in DSC cell (-10 °C/min precisely).

Fig. 3 shows the DSC thermograms (all scanned 10 °C/min) of the melt-crystallized sPS samples subjected to (top to bottom) 260, 250, and 240oC, respectively. The multiple

Fig. 3 DSC thermograms (10 °C/min) of the s-PS samples. melting peaks in 240oC melt-crystallized sPS reflect a combination of α and β -crystals. By comparison, the reduced number of melting peaks in 250oC or 260 oC melt-crystallized sPS

reflects a fact that the α -crystal decreases or disappear completely as sPS is crystallized at increasingly higher temperatures.

CONCLUSION

Melt-crystallization at lower temperatures (240 °C or lower) produced combination of α -type (Peak-2, and -3) and β -type (Peak-1) crystals. Generally speaking, lower crystallization temperature favors α -type while higher temperature favors β -type, leading to various fractions of α and β -types depending on temperature of melt crystallization. For melt-crystallized s-PS subjected to further annealing at higher temperatures, more fraction of original α -type may be transformed to β -type but not vice versa.

Unique thermal treatments were performed and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and X-ray diffraction analysis were used to characterize the dominating crystal form(s) being developed in cold-crystallized syndiotactic polystyrene (sPS) in comparison with melt-crystallized polystyrene. X-ray result suggested that cold-crystallization at higher than 200 °C (200-250 °C) produced only α -type crystal (or majority). More details will be reported in future. More detailed results/discussion are being organized and to be reported in full papers.

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